

EARTH SCIENCES

IMPROVEMENT OF FRACTURE SIMULATOR OUTPUT DATA FOR HYBRID AND MULTIFRACTURE CASES

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Abstract

The purpose of the work is to determine the way to work with fracture simulator output data for cases complicated by stage-by-stage processing calculations. Hydraulic fracturing databases are designed to store a single numerical parameter, which causes complications when there are several values in the output data set. The way to obtain a correct estimation of the designated case by a single parameter will allow to apply the results of calculations in the statistical analysis of hydraulic fracturing.

Scientific novelty of the work lies in the definition of a new method for working with the output data of the hydraulic fracturing simulator. The scope of application includes the case of formation of several fractures, as well as several calculations relating to one fracture. As a result, a method of working with data has been developed, which allows filling the standardized data set regardless of the number of elements in the output data of the hydraulic fracturing simulator.

Keywords: fracture simulator, hybrid fracturing, heterogeneous fracturing, fracture analysis, lumped fracture model, data processing.

Qualitative analysis of performed hydraulic fracturing includes preparation of data, including those obtained as a result of calculations in the simulator [1]. Parameters should be expressed as numerical variables corresponding to each data channel. Uncertainties arise when several values for one variable are obtained [2].

The conductivity of the fracture, which affects the resulting effect, depends on proppant fixation or dissolving the walls of the fracture with acid [3]. As general, it is an optional choice of technology, but it is also possible to use hybrid fracturing, when the conductivity is created simultaneously by acid and proppant particles [4]. When simulating such a process in a standard hydraulic fracturing simulator, two sets of output data with different structure result [5].

Subsequent work with the output data is possible if there is a single variable value. The following approach is suggested:

1. Volume of slurry and clean liquid, mass of proppant, net pressure, proppant fixed length, fracture width is taken equal to the proppant data set;
2. Hydraulic fracture length, acid-etched fracture length and dissolved rock volume is taken equal to the acid data set;
3. Fracture fluid efficiency and average hydraulic fracture width are taken as the average of the data sets;
4. Total fracture height is the maximum value from the data sets;

5. Fracture conductivity - the sum of values from the data sets.

As a result of data processing in the method presented above, reasonable values of the variables can be obtained when modeling acid-fracturing [6, 7].

Another case of occurrence of several values is hydraulic fracturing of several intervals separated by a considerable distance [8, 9]. In this case, obtaining single variable values is possible according to the following principle:

1. Volume of slurry and clean fluid, mass by fractions, total fracture height, fracture conductivity and volume of dissolved rock is taken as the sum of the values;
2. Fluid efficiency, net pressure, fracture length, average hydraulic fracture width, fixed width is taken as the average value;
3. Hydraulic fracture length to assess the possible radius of coverage - the maximum value.

The applicability of the proposed methods is limited to hybrid fracturing and simultaneous processing of several intervals, provided that pseudo-3D fracture models and simulators based on it are used [10].

Conclusions:

1. A way of working with the output data of the fracture simulator for some cases, in which there is uncertainty of the values of variables, is proposed.

2. Application of the method allows using standard software to prepare data for acid-proppant fracturing analysis similar to classic hydraulic fracturing and acid hydraulic fracturing.

3. The statistical analysis carried out on the results of processing the data prepared by the proposed method will allow to compare fairly the standard and hybrid hydraulic fracturing technologies carried out in the considered area of development.

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